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HOLLAND BLOORVIEW KIDS REHABILITATION
HOSPITAL

RECIPIENT

F Virginia Wright (Nov 22, 2022 15:13 EST)

Signed

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22.11.2022

Date

SCHEDULE A – LICENSED WORK

Licensed Work: Interprofessional Socialization and Valuing Scale - 21 (ISVS-21)

Original Authors: Gillian King, Carole Orchard, Hossein Khalili

Description: There is a need for measures of interprofessional socialization (IS) to investigate the role of interprofessional education in preparing health care students and practitioners to take part in interprofessional health care teams. The 21-item Interprofessional Socialization and Valuing Scale (ISVS-21) is a refined measure (from a previously published 24-item measure) that can be used with practitioners and students. Two equivalent 9-item forms (ISVS-9A and ISVS-9B) can be used for pre-post study to assess change in IS after interprofessional education.

Publication Restrictions: None

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